

**PARTICIPATION OF FARMERS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF
MAHATMAGANDHI NATIONAL RURAL EMPLOYMENT
GUARANTEE SCHEME**

Dr. AbbasahebV.Kalyankar
Principal

**Late Kalpana Chawala Arts and Science
Mahila Sr. College.
Gangakhed .Dist. Parbhani**

Introduction :

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme is implemented by the ministry of rural development under the provision of Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGS). The act coming into implementation on 2 Feb 2006. Firstly it was introduced in 200 hundred districts out of that most of the districts were under the category of backward districts of the country. Later on in the second step it was introduced in additional 130 districts in the year 2007-2008 and lastly the scheme was extended to all districts of the country from 1st April 2008 actually at present it was implemented in 625 districts in the country. The unique features of the act include time bound employment guarantee for 100 days in a financial year and wage payment within 15 days.

The main objective of scheme is to augmenting wage employment and secondary objective is strengthening the natural resources management the Indian economy mostly is based on agriculture. Agriculture sector creates more employment opportunities in comparisons to other sectors as industries and commerce India is second over populated country in the world next to china. food problem can be solve through the agriculture sector only.

In India, in modern days, even in 21st century, people, particularly the farmers are succeeding.

The succeeding problem in agriculture sectors is very serious. Too many research people have studied problem and come to conclusion to the basic reason is decrease

in financial passion of the farmers one of the basic problem in agricultural is on unviability of labors now the trend of wage worker is diverting to other field like cities and factories rather than agriculture and therefore problem is created as unavailability of labor in agriculture business. Labors are eager to shift rather than agriculture due two reasons, firstly labor work in agriculture is very hard and secondly the rate of wage payment is low. In such conditions this schemes should be forcible to implement in agriculture.

Assumptions :

- 1) Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme can be implemented in agriculture sector only.
- 2) It is useful in financial developments of the farmers.
- 3) It is essential to control the succeeding the agriculturist.
- 4) This scheme is useful to total development of agriculture.
- 5) To reduce the contrivance between the unemployment problem, and efficiency in agriculture labor.

Period of research and scope of the subject :

The research period for study is considered from 2006 to 2012 for six years development of agriculture sector through coordinating between farmer and agriculture labor.

Research method :

The present research is depends on the primary and secondary resources Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme and deficiency in agriculture labor has been studied jointly research people have visited many of the villages to study economical position and agriculture business of the farmers

Objectives of research :

- 1) To implement this scheme in agriculture sectors.
- 2) To solve the problem of deficiency in agriculture labor.

- 3) Labor utilized in the scheme is to be used for productive purpose.
- 4) Correlations between the implementation of scheme with agriculture sector.
- 5) Concentration on creating labor in agriculture sector.
- 6) The scheme should be implementing for strengthening the agriculture production in rural areas.
- 7) The effect of implementation of this scheme in rural area should be useful in increasing agriculture production

Conclusion :

Unviability of minimum labor required in agriculture sector is a serious problem throughout India it effects on agriculture productivity due to unviability of labor agriculture business has become very serious primarily agriculture is depend on nature and secondly unviability of labor these two are crises in agriculture production, therefore agriculture program cannot implemented in time and agriculture program totally collapse. Second problem can be controlled by implementing the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme properly now it is education facilities at all level are sufficiently available throughout India these educated people are searching employment in other sectors rather than agriculture.

Recommendations :

- 1) Selection of work should be sanctioned in Gram Sabha of panchayat instead of only the elected members of the committee.
- 2) The work selected for implementation of this scheme should useful for agriculture productivity in rural areas.
- 3) 70% reservations should be given to backward communities like SC, ST, others and 50% reservations should for ladies
- 4) In all states of India farmers people use to taint in the farmer, government employment guarantee schemes has employee.
- 5) Correlation between the unemployment and unavailability of labor in agriculture should achieve by government few appointing a special committee.
- 6) Labor in the scheme should be utilized only for agriculture productivity purposes only

- 7) A special committee of farmers should be appointed in every village that committee should have to take record of the available labors and provides in proper share .

Reference :

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- 2) Warshik 2012 Maharashtra, Editor: Tukram Jadhav, the unique academic pune.
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